

**SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF 1(4-AMINOPHENYL)-2(P-
CHLOROPHENYL THIOCARBAMIDO)-1-ETHANOL**

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ABSTRACT

Pharmaceutically active drugs are crucial part of today's generation. Due to huge population of the world responsibility of the chemist increase toward produce active molecules. Thiocarbamide moieties have various pharmaceutical and industrial significances. Present research scheme designed to synthesize 1(4-aminophenyl)-2(4-chlorophenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol by the interactions of 4-(2-amino-1-hydroxyethyl) aniline and p-chlorophenyl isothiocyanate in acetone medium, to isolate 1(4-aminophenyl)-2 (p-chlorophenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol. Characterized of this synthesized molecules on the basis of conventional elemental analysis, chemical characteristics and through IR, PMR, CMR and Mass spectral analysis. Confirmed the structure of synthesized molecule from spectral data.

KEYWORDS: 4-(2-amino-1-hydroxyethyl) aniline, p-chlorophenyl isothiocyanate, thiocarbamide, 1(4-aminophenyl)-2 (p-chlorophenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol.

INTRODUCTION

Now a day's world population enhance rapidly along with this demand of potent drugs increases. World researchers were pointed their attention toward this aspect and working with challenge toward same. Pathogens are become resistive against existing some drugs moieties thus have a great need to developed more active and potent drugs moieties with good solubility, diffusion and activity that will be demonstrate effective pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics of drugs. The literature survey divulges that from last couple of decades' numerous advances, theories and new concepts regarding to synthesis of novel moieties, chemical, physical as well as biological study of benzenoid and non-benzenoid, heteroacyclic and heterocyclic compounds were studied.^[1-5] These compounds have their own identity and importance in the chemical and life sciences due to their variety of applications in

medicinal, agricultural, pharmaceutical, industrial, biotechnological and biochemical sciences.^[6-10] If we think about the drugs we can define the history of medicine by these compounds.

In the view of the utilities of substituted thiocarbamide compounds in various fields like chemical industry, analytical, pharmaceuticals, metallurgy, textile applications and as a part of present research work, recently being undertaken in this laboratory in the synthesis of nitrogen, nitrogen and sulphur containing heteroacycles and heterocycles and to investigate their medicinal, pharmaceutical, agricultural, industrial, biotechnological and biochemical significance^[11-18], hence interactions of 4-(2-amino-1-hydroxyethyl)aniline and p-chlorophenyl sothiocyanate in acetone medium, to isolate 1(4-aminophenyl)-2 (p-chlorophenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanols.

METHODS AND MATERIAL

All AR grade chemicals were used throughout experiment.

Synthesis of 1(4-aminophenyl)-2(p-chlorophenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol

4-(2-amino-1-hydroxyethyl) aniline and p-chlorophenyl isothiocyanate are reflux in acetone medium for 2 hrs to obtained 1(4-aminophenyl)-2(p-chlorophenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol. After completion of reaction, to isolated 1(4-aminophenyl)-2(p-chlorophenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol from solvent. After distillation of acetone the product is isolated which is recrystallized from ethanol to get white colour crystalline solid with m.p. 85°C.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Properties of 1(4-aminophenyl)-2(p-chlorophenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol

1(4-aminophenyl)-2(p-chlorophenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol is white crystalline compound. C₁₄H₁₆N₃SOCl with m.p. 85°C. It gave positive test for nitrogen, chlorine and Sulphur. Soluble in boiled sodium hydroxide, sulphuric acid, 1,4-dioxane, ethanol, acetone and benzene and was sparingly soluble in water. Formed picrates having melting point 92°C.

Elemental analysis (mass %): C- 54.88, H-5.21, Cl- 11.44, N-13.56, O- 5.16 and S-10.35.

FTIR spectrum (ν cm⁻¹): The IR spectrum of compound was carried out in **KBr pellets** on **SHIMADZU IR spectrometer**¹⁹⁻²⁴. 2773. 64-2565.33 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 2902.87 (Aromatic C-H stretching), 1945.82 (N-C=S stretching), 1897.95 (C=S stretching), 3050.95 (Two N-H stretching), 3195.83 (Alcoholic O-H stretching), 1180.72-1244.50 (C-O stretching), 1505.55-1294.24 (Aliphatic -H bending), 1070.49 (C-C stretching). **PMR spectrum data:** The PMR spectrum of a compound was recorded in CDCl₃+ DMSO_d₆ on **Bruker Advance-II 400 NMR spectrometer**.^[19-20,25-30] This spectrum distinctly displayed the signals, due to four aromatic protons of amino substituted phenyl ring in the range at δ 7.413 - δ 7.452 ppm of phenyl group, four aromatic protons of chlorine substituted phenyl ring in the range at δ 7.482 - δ 7.550 ppm, alcoholic -H at δ 4.63 ppm, (C-H) proton at δ 3.493 ppm, two amino -NH protons at δ 6.725-7.102 ppm, two diastereotopic methylene protons at δ 3.235-3.433 ppm and NH Proton at δ 7.352 - 7.546 ppm.

CONCLUSION

Amino and chloro substituted phenyl ring along with thiocarbamido nuclei are significantly used in different field. In present work data obtained from chemical characteristics, elemental and spectral analysis reveal that newly synthesized present compound was assigned the structure as 1(4-aminophenyl)-2(chlorophenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol. This work create scope to studies various chemical, pharmaceutical, agricultural and biological applications of newly

synthesized 1(4-aminophenyl)-2(chlorophenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol. The final structure shown as follow.

1(4-aminophenyl)-2(p-chlorophenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol

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